

A New Synthesis of Propylure

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Periodic acid cleavage of the monoepoxide of 1,5-cyclooctadiene provides a key intermediate useful in the synthesis of several long chain carbon compounds. The total synthesis of 1-acetoxy-10-*n*-propyltridecatrans-5,9-diene, the proposed structure of propylure, has been accomplished using several novel synthetic methods. The efficiency of the synthesis is demonstrated by a 25% yield of the compound. The spectroscopic properties of the synthetic propylure were identical to that of the reported attractant.

PROPYLURE was reportedly isolated from virgin female pink bollworm moths several years ago. The structure was established as 1-acetoxy-10-*n*-propyltrideca-*trans* 5, 9-diene (I)¹. The apparent biological activity and its unique structure prompted several workers to synthesise propylure. As a result there are a number of syntheses of the compound reported to date¹⁻⁷. The first reported synthetic propylure was obtained in 0.2% overall yield¹. A second synthesis involving a seven step reaction afforded propylure in a 1% overall conversion². Subsequently, Stowell³ reported a single step synthesis for propylure in 7% overall yield. Several subsequent syntheses⁴⁻⁷ for propylure were likewise characterized by low yields, product mixtures, and expensive starting materials which are not readily available. We report here a convenient

of steps employed for this synthesis could provide information and insight for the synthesis of long chain carbon compounds. The introduction of ethylenic linkage in long chain saturated aliphatic compounds though possible, involves tedious and lengthy processes. The present work would provide methods to synthesize compounds with ethylenic linkage at the desired position starting with suitable olefinic compounds.

Epoxidation of 1, 5-cyclooctadiene (II) with peroxyacetic acid gave predominantly the monoepoxide 4, 5-epoxycyclooctene. The small quantity of diepoxide formed was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The monoepoxide was cleaved with periodic acid in aqueous medium to give the eight carbon *cis* dialdehyde(III)⁸. The dialdehyde (III) upon reduction

and economic synthesis of propylure in 25% yield starting from readily available materials. Periodic acid cleavage of epoxides to yield dialdehydes⁸ provided the incentive to synthesize propylure economically. The entire synthetic sequence is built on the extension of the chain length using *cis*-4-octene-1, 8-dial.

with sodium borohydride in ethanol yielded the dialcohol (IV). One of the hydroxyl groups on the dialcohol was blocked with dihydropyran to give the monopyranyl ether (V). The free hydroxyl group on (V) was brominated with phosphorous tribromide. The bromo pyranylether (VI), was reacted with triphenyl phosphine to

The physiological activity of propylure is questionable. Recent work by Shorey⁹ implies that synthetic propylure failed to exhibit any biological activity as reported by previous workers either in the laboratory or in field test. In the light of this recent observation, the utility of synthetic propylure is limited. However, the sequence

yield the phosphonium salt which later was condensed with 4-heptanone in the presence of sodium methoxide to yield 9-(*n*-propyl)-1-pyranoxy-*cis*-4, 8-dodecadiene (VII).

In a previous synthesis of propylure⁶, the tri-substituted double bond was introduced at an early stage in the synthetic route using a Reformatsky reaction followed by an elimination step. This approach led to the formation of isomers, from which the desired positional isomer had to be separated prior to further reaction. If the separation was not completed at this stage the final product might be contaminated with *cis* and *trans* compounds of the undesired materials such as (VIII). The dihydropranyl blocking group on (VII)

was removed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the resulting alcohol (IX) was brominated with phosphorous tribromide. This 1-bromo-9-(*n*-propyl)-*cis*-4, 8-dodecadiene (X) was converted to the corresponding nitrile (XI) with sodium cyanide.

(IX) R = -OH ; (X) R = -Br , (XI) R = -C≡N

The nitrile (XI) was reduced by a metal ion borohydride reduction¹⁰ using cobalt chloride hexahydrate and sodium borohydride to give the primary amine (XII). The amine (XII) upon diazotization with

sodium nitrite at 0° to -5° gave the alcohol (XIII). The final product (I) was obtained upon esterification of (XIII) with acetyl chloride. The isomerization of the *cis* to the active *trans* form was effected using selenium⁶. Most of the synthetic steps yielded products in over 90% yield. However, the overall yield was considerably lower due to the poor yield in the Wittig coupling step (VIII). Due to the ambiguous physiological activity of propylure, further attempts to improve the yield of the Wittig coupling step were not investigated.

The identity of the synthetic compound was established through the comparison of its I.R. and NMR spectra with that of the authentic sample.² In the I.R. spectrum the maxima at 1745, 1245 and 1040 cm^{-1} are characteristic of a primary acetate group. A strong band at 970 cm^{-1} is characteristic of the C-H out of plane deformation of the *trans*-disubstituted double bond.^{2,5}

Experimental

4-Octene-1, 8-diol (IV). To a solution of 28 g (0.2m) of the dialdehyde⁹ in 250ml ethanol, 9.0g (0.2m) of sodium borohydride was added in small amounts

(XII) R = -CH₂NH₂ ; (XIII) R = -CH₂-OH

(45 min.), the contents were stirred for one hour and were poured into a liter of water. The aqueous solution was extracted successively three times with 100 ml of chloroform. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. Evaporation of the chloroform gave 28.0 g (97%) of the 4-octene-1, 8-diol. NMR (neat) δ 1.7 (j, 4H), 2.1 (m, 4H), 3.6 (t, 4H), 4.9 (s, 2H), 5.4 (t, 2H). (Found C. 66.61; H. 11.18; calc. for $C_8H_{16}O_2$, C. 66.66; H. 11.11).

8-(tetrahydro-2-pyranoxy)-cis-4-octenol (V). To a solution of 25 g (0.17m) of (IV) in 200 ml anhydrous ether was added dropwise, with stirring, a mixture of 14 g (0.16 m) of dihydropyran and 0.5 g of *p*-toluene-sulfonic acid in 100 ml ether. Following the addition, it was allowed to stir at room temperature for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered. The ether layer was washed with 0.1 m sodium bicarbonate and was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. Evaporation of the dried ether gave 35.7 g (94%) of (V) as a pale yellow liquid. NMR (neat) δ 1.75 (m, 10H), 2.0 (m, 4H), 3.5 (m, 7H), 4.5 (s, 1H), 5.4 (t, 2H).

1-bromo-8-(tetrahydro-2-pyranoxy)-4-octene (VI). To a solution of 35 g (0.15 m) of (V) in 100 ml dry benzene was added dropwise, with stirring, a solution of 52.1 g (0.2 m) of phosphorus tribromide in 50 ml benzene. The temperature was maintained throughout the addition at 10° using an ice bath. Following the addition of phosphorus tribromide, the reaction mixture was allowed to stir for one hour. Later it was refluxed at 80° for 2 hr. while adding more benzene to keep the amount of benzene constant at 100 ml. Then the mixture was cooled in an ice bath and 50 g of ice were added to the reaction mixture. The benzene layer was washed with 0.1 m sodium bicarbonate, sodium chloride, and water. The benzene layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and removed by distillation. The yield was 42.8 g (96%) of (VI). NMR (neat) δ 1.7 (m, 10H), 2.1 (m, 4H), 3.5 (m, 7H), 5.4 (t, 2H) (Mol. wt. found 289, calc for $C_{18}H_{28}O_2$ Br 290.9).

1-(tetrahydro-2-pyranoxy)-9-(n-propyl)-cis-4, 8-dodecadiene (VII). A mixture of 42 g (0.14 m) of (VI), 52.6 g (0.2 m) triphenylphosphine, and 250 ml of dimethylformamide was heated with stirring for 4 hr. at 105°. The phosphonium salt which precipitated was filtered and was washed quickly with benzene. The salt was immediately put into a dry flask along with 100 ml of methanol. To this stirring mixture were added 20 ml portions of a solution of 22.8 g (0.2 m) of 4-heptanone, and 1.1 g of sodium methoxide in 200 ml methanol. The reaction mixture was gently warmed to 30° during the addition. After the addition was completed it was stirred for 30 min at 35° and diluted with 200 ml water. The contents were allowed to stand in a refrigerator for 24 hr. The solution was extracted with ether and dried over sodium sulfate. The solvent was stripped to yield 28 g (63%) of (VII). NMR (neat) δ 0.97 (m, 6H), 1.6 (m, 12H), 2.1 (m, 10H), 3.7 (m, 5H), 5.4-5.6 (m, 3H).

1-Hydroxy-9-(n-propyl)-4, 8-dodecadiene (IX). A suspension of 20.5 g (0.06 m) of (VII) in 100 ml of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid was gently refluxed at 70° for 4 hr. Following this it was neutralized with sodium hydroxide. The neutral solution was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with 50 ml portions of chloroform three times. The chloroform layer was washed with water, dried over sodium sulfate, and stripped to yield 14.5 g (97%) of the free alcohol (IX). NMR (neat) δ 1.0 (m, 6H), 1.7 (m, 6H), 2.1 (m, 10H), 3.8 (t, 2H), 4.6 (s, 1H), 5.5-5.7 (m, 3H). (Mol. wt. found 225; calc for $C_{18}H_{34}O$, 224).

1-Bromo-9-(n-propyl)-4, 8-dodecadiene (X). A solution of 14.5 g (0.06 m) of (IX) in 100 ml dry benzene in an ice bath was treated dropwise while stirring with 18 g (0.06 m) of phosphorous tribromide. After the addition of phosphorous tribromide, it was allowed to stir at room temperature for 1 hr and later refluxed at 80° for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, treated with 10 g of ice and the benzene layer was separated. The benzene layer was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. The benzene was removed using a rotatory evaporator to give 17.2 g (92.5%) of (X). NMR (neat) δ 1.0 (m, 6H), 1.7 (m, 6H), 2.1 (m, 10H), 3.8 (m, 2H), 5.4-5.8 (m, 3H). (Mol. wt. found 287; calc for $C_{18}H_{27}Br$ 286.9).

1-Cyano-9-(n-propyl)-4, 8-dodecadiene (XI). The bromoalkene (X), 14.5 g (0.05 m), dissolved in 100 ml ethanol was stirred with 10 g (0.2 m) of sodium cyanide for 48 hours at 50°. The mixture was washed with 100 ml of water and extracted three times with 50 ml portions of ether. The ether was stripped to give a brownish liquid 10.3 g (87%). NMR (neat) δ 1.0 (m, 6H), 1.65 (m, 8H), 2.0 (m, 10H), 5.5-5.8 (m, 3H).

1-Amino-10-(n-propyl)-cis-5, 8-tridecadiene (XII). The nitrile (XI), 10 g (0.04 m), dissolved in 200 ml ethanol was treated with 24 g of cobalt chloride hexahydrate and 19 g (0.5 m) of sodium borohydride at room temperature. Evolution of hydrogen gas accompanied the formation of a black precipitate. After the addition of borohydride the solution was stirred at room temperature for 2 hr, and the reaction mixture was treated with 300 ml of 3 N hydrochloric acid. The ethanol was removed by distillation. The water layer was extracted with ether to remove any unreacted nitrile. The water layer was neutralized with 0.1 N ammonium hydroxide and extracted with ether. The ether was removed by distillation to yield 9.06 g (89%) of the amine (XII). NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 1.1 (m, 6H), 1.5 (m, 8H), 2.2 (m, 12H), 5.4-5.8 (m, 3H). (Mol. wt. found 238; calc for $C_{18}H_{31}N$, 237).

1-Hydroxy-10-(n-propyl) trideca-5, 9-diene (XIII). To 9.4 g (0.038 m) of (XII) in 400 ml water was added 50 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid with constant cooling. To the clear solution ice was added to lower the temperature to 0°. Later, to the cold solution 17 g (25 m) of sodium nitrite in 30 ml water was added

slowly. After the addition was completed the solution was stirred for 20 min and later 100 g of ice and 1 g of urea were added to it. The solution was dropped into a distillation apparatus containing anhydrous sodium sulfate at the same rate as the distillate was being collected. The temperature was 135°. The distillate was extracted three times with 100 ml portions of ether. The residue was treated with 53 ml of 2.0 *N* sodium hydroxide, filtered and neutralized with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The neutral solution was extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts were washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The ether upon evaporation yielded 8.6 g (95%) of the alcohol (XIII). NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.0 (t, 6H), 1.6 (m, 8H), 2.0 (m, 10H), 3.6 (t, 2H), 5.4-5.8 (m, 3H).

1-Acetoxy-10-(n-propyl) trideca-5, 9-diene (I): The alcohol (XIII), 4.6 g (9.02 m), dissolved in 100 ml dry benzene was cooled in an ice bath to 0°. Acetyl chloride, 3.9 g (0.050 m), was dropped into the cold benzene solution slowly with constant stirring. The mixture was stirred in the cold for one hour. The flask was fitted with a reflux condenser, a calcium chloride guard tube and allowed to stand for 8 hr. at room temperature. The mixture was then poured in 100 g of cracked ice. A pale yellow liquid separated. It was washed with cold (0.1 m) sodium bicarbonate solution and dried over anhydrous silica gel. Yield 5.2 g (96%).

Isomerization to yield the trans form of propolure. A mixture of 0.17 g selenium powder and 2.2 g of (I) were heated in an evacuated sealed tube at 250° for 4 hr. Upon washing the tube with ether, concentrating the solution and then distilling at 128° (0.8 mm), 2 g (91%) of the product was obtained. The product exhibited a strong absorption peak at 970 cm⁻¹ associated with the C-H out of plane deformation of *trans* disubstituted double bonds³. NMR (CCl₄) 0.95 (t, 6H), 1.45 (m, 8H), 2.0 (m, 13H), 4.1 (t, 2H), 5.4-5.7 (m, 3H). IR (film)

2950-2910, 1745, 1245, 1040, 970 cm⁻¹. (Found C, 76.93; H, 11.47. Calc for C₁₃H₂₂O₂: C, 77.10; H, 11.49.).

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11. Reported physical constants are uncorrected. All chemicals used were reagent grade or purified before use. Microanalysis was performed by Galbraith Laboratories of Knoxville, Tennessee. NMR spectra were taken on a Varian A-60 using tetramethylsilane as standard. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-10 and Perkin Elmer IR-700. Molecular weights were determined using a Du Pont 21-490 Mass Spectrometer.